

THE PROPERTIES AND APPLICATIONS OF SHORT STAPLE

ALUMINA FIBRE REINFORCED ALUMINIUM ALLOYS

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Summary

High volume industrial applications are currently being developed for metal matrix composites (MMC's) to take advantage of the availability of low cost, strong (2000 MPa), high modulus (300 GPa), staple alumina fibres. Advances made in the areas of fibre preform technology and composite fabrication have already resulted in the commercialization of MMC's in pistons for diesel engines. The properties of composites produced by a squeeze casting process are described with particular reference to the piston application and preliminary data on billets made by a powder metallurgical route are reported. Near theoretical modulus enhancement, considerable improvement of high temperature strength and superior wear properties are some of the advantages conferred on aluminium alloys. In order to take full advantage of the reinforcement capability of the fibres at temperatures below 200°C it may be necessary to modify alloy chemistry and composite heat treatment.

Introduction

Over the last decade ICI PLC has developed the manufacture of short staple, polycrystalline alumina fibres which are sold under the trade name 'Saffil'. The main commercial application is the insulation of high temperature industrial furnaces. In recent years however, improved grades of these fibres have been developed for use in metal matrix composites. The relatively low cost of the fibres at around \$30/kg and their availability in large tonnage quantities has attracted the attention of engineering companies wishing to develop pistons and other components for high performance diesel engines.

Short fibre reinforcement of aluminium alloys provides an elegant and cost-effective solution to a problem which has beset design engineers for years, namely the cracking of pistons with re-entrant combustion chambers. This form of chamber or bowl for direct injection diesel engines offers advantages in thermal efficiency, emissions and noise over more conventional types (1). Unfortunately, such designs also highlight a difficult materials problem since the bowl edge temperature may approach 500°C and aluminium alloys suffer a rapid loss of strength at temperatures over 200°C. In addition to the high temperatures, the crown is subjected to severe thermal and mechanical cyclic stresses which give rise to cracking. The problem may be solved by the incorporation of fibre preforms using a squeeze casting process to reinforce selectively the highly stressed combustion bowl area; engine trials have confirmed predictions of considerably extended lifetimes under very severe operating conditions.

The concept of selective reinforcement of aluminium has already been commercialized by Toyota Motor Company to reinforce the ring land area of diesel pistons (2). New piston designs with improved heat flow characteristics and reduced weight lead to problems with seizure of the top ring land and cylinder bore, and excessive wear of the ring groove. Fibre reinforcement is used to improve the wear resistance of aluminium alloys and to increase mechanical durability at elevated temperatures.

This paper reviews the selection criteria adopted to meet specific technical targets for the two piston applications described above and also considers an alternative route to metal matrix composites using a powder metallurgical method.

Fibre Production and Properties

The alumina fibres are produced as short staple by a spinning process which controls the fibre diameter within tight limits around a median value of 3 microns. Contrary to methods employed to prepare whiskers and melt-spun ceramic fibres, this process results in a very low level of non-fibrous material. A typical diameter distribution is given in Figure 1 and this uniformity is illustrated by the scanning electron micrograph in Figure 2. A fine grained microstructure is developed by incorporating about 4% silica and by close attention to each heat treatment stage during fibre production. The silica is effective in enabling a controlled progression through the transition alumina forms, thus facilitating the removal of porosity, and by acting as a crystal growth inhibitor once the transformation to the alpha alumina phase occurs.

Figure 1. A typical fibre diameter distribution

Figure 2. SEM showing uniformity of fibre diameters

Fibre in the delta alumina form (RF grade) has a tensile strength of 2000 MPa, a modulus of 300 GPa and a density of 3.3 g/cm³. Further processing at high temperatures causes the gradual conversion of the delta phase to the alpha alumina form with a corresponding increase in hardness, modulus and density, and a decrease in strength. The loss of strength is due to a step increase in crystal size associated with the phase transformation. The flexibility of the production process allows the concentration of the alpha alumina form to be controlled and the properties of the fibre to be tailored to meet the demands of the reinforcement application. The graphs in Figure 3 exemplify this point.

Figure 3. Showing the effect of alpha alumina concentration on fibre strength, modulus and hardness

Composite Fabrication

In recent years major advances have been made in both squeeze casting and powder metallurgical techniques for producing metal matrix composites, but the economics of the two routes at the present time mean that they are serving two separate industries. Whereas squeeze casting has been developed mainly by the automobile industry producing net-shape components, powder-based composites have been targeted more towards the production of billets suitable for secondary forming shapes for military and aerospace applications. For these short staple alumina fibres both techniques are applicable but, to-date, more attention has been devoted to producing squeeze cast materials to meet more immediate and very specific application requirements. Indeed it should be stressed that the results reported here for the powder composites should be regarded as preliminary, and significant improvements are anticipated as processing conditions are optimised. Since the powder-based materials were made by a proprietary process only details of the squeeze casting procedure are given.

Fibre Preforms

As stated earlier, selected area reinforcement in squeeze cast components is achieved by means of liquid metal infiltration of fibre preforms. The preforms are made by slurrying fibres of controlled length in water along with small amounts of inorganic binder and a fugitive organic binder followed by forming the required shape in a paper making-type process. The procedure can be used to control the lay-down which determines the fibre orientation in the composite, and the preform density determines the volume fraction of fibres. The inorganic binder, in the form of silica, is used to give good handling strength after burning off the fugitive binder and to enable machining to tight tolerances. Good compressive strength is important to resist permanent deformation during the high pressure casting process. An ability to match accurately the preform shape to the shape of the finished component is needed since the target, in pistons for example, is net-shape castings requiring the minimum of finishing. The schematic diagram in Figure 4 shows the orientations which may be achieved in the preforms and the photograph in Figure 5 shows some of the simple shapes which are used. For the type of orientation illustrated by the disc-shaped preforms in Figure 4, the density of the preforms may be controlled easily over the range 0.15-1.0 g/cm³, equivalent to a fibre loading in the composite of 4.5-30 v/o. Higher preform densities may be achieved but with a corresponding decrease in fibre length. For preform rings with the alternative fibre orientation the maximum density achievable to-date is around 0.25 g/cm³.

Infiltration of Preforms

Various papers have been published (3-5) describing the essential elements of the squeeze casting process and the techno-commercial advantages over other fabrication techniques. The process minimises materials and energy utilisation, offering net-shape components with improved mechanical properties. All types of aluminium alloys available for casting or forging may be employed. Composites are made by placing the preforms into a die cavity and infiltrating with molten alloy by means of a driven ram assembly. The preforms, die and ram are preheated before introduction of the melt at a known degree of superheat. Complete infiltration is found to proceed very rapidly under a pressure of around 30 MPa to produce pore-free composites with excellent fibre-matrix bonding.

This pressure should not be regarded as optimum since higher pressures are normally used in industrial practice (70-120 MPa), particularly when more complex shapes are involved, and theoretical considerations predict that much lower values may be adequate. Billets described in this paper were prepared either at the University of Surrey, Guildford, UK in an experimental infiltration rig (6) or by a Japanese company using production squeeze casting equipment. In each case the fibre orientation was essentially random planar. Typical billet dimensions were 100 mm diameter x 15 mm thickness.

Figure 4. Schematic diagram showing possible orientations in preforms

Figure 5. Photograph showing simple preform shapes used for piston reinforcement

Composite Properties

Piston Alloys

Aluminium-silicon alloys are the traditional choice for piston applications due to their high fluidity and good balance of thermal and mechanical properties. In this present study an alloy with similar properties but with the composition Al-9Si-3Cu (JIS Type AC8B) was selected and squeeze cast composite billets containing 12, 18 and 24 v/o fibre were prepared. The billets were given a standard T6 heat treatment and tensile specimens extracted for testing up to 450°C. The tensile strength and modulus data are plotted in Figures 6 and 7 along with comparative data for the unreinforced alloy. Property data obtained are related to the use of the fibre to reinforce the combustion bowl and ring groove areas of pistons.

Figure 6. Effect of temperature on the tensile strength of Al-9Si-3Cu-based composites

Figure 7. Effect of temperature on the modulus of Al-9Si-3Cu-based composites

It will be noted that at 25°C the modulus increases almost linearly with increasing volume fraction of fibre over the range 0.12 to 0.24, however, there is no significant change in the strength of the unreinforced alloy. As the test temperature was raised so the strain to failure values were found to increase from around 0.5% at 25°C to 1.1-1.4% at 300°C. All three composites show excellent retention of strength and modulus up to 300°C, with the highest volume fraction material having a modulus 30% higher than the unreinforced alloy at 25°C and retaining approximately 80% of its original strength. Composite properties decay as the temperature is

raised to 450°C, but the materials retain sufficient strength and stiffness to overcome the crown cracking problems associated with re-entrant-type combustion bowls. The photograph in Figure 8 shows a sectioned piston with this design of bowl.

As expected, hardness of the composites is related to the volume fraction of fibre as illustrated by the data given in Table I below.

Table I. Hardness Values at 25°C

Volume fraction of fibre	Vickers Hardness No (HV10)
0	131
0.12	179
0.18	190
0.24	212

The coefficient of thermal expansion of the metal is reduced by incorporating fibres, as shown by the results in Table II measured normal and parallel to the planes of fibre orientation. While it is important not to have too great a difference between the reinforced and unreinforced areas in a piston, it is generally advantageous to have a reduction in expansion since this allows a closer fit to the cylinder bore and results in improved fuel economy.

Table II. Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (α)

Volume fraction of fibre	α (in plane) ($10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$)	α (normal) ($10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$)
0	2.03	2.03
0.12	1.66	1.76
0.18	1.54	1.66
0.24	1.55	1.57

The wear data (7) reported in Fig 10 are based on a different alloy to that described in earlier work. The tests were carried out on an aluminium alloy containing 12% silicon and reinforced with 4.4% v/o alumina fibre. The composites were contacted with a cylindrical mating element of chromium steel rotating at a speed of 0.3 m/sec under a load of 20 kg/mm² for a period of 1 hour.

The results provide a good illustration of the need to obtain the correct balance of fibre properties for optimum composite performance, in this case for the reinforcement of the ring groove area of diesel pistons. (See the sectioned piston in Fig 9). Examination of the data show that not only is the wear of the composite very much lower than the unreinforced alloy (10-20 microns compared with more than 700 microns), but that it is possible to achieve a similar wear of the mating surface as the pure

alloy by limiting the level of the alpha alumina phase to within the range 20-30%. This observation is very important since excessive wear of the piston rings must be avoided. While these results are highly encouraging, further work is needed to improve our fundamental understanding of the wear mechanisms at play and to determine the potential for their application on a broader front.

Figures 8 and 9. Showing reinforced combustion bowl (by courtesy of the AE Group) and ring groove (taken from a news release by Toyota Motor Corp) areas of sectioned pistons

Figure 10. Wear data for Al-12Si alloy reinforced with 4.4% fibre against chromium-steel mating surface

Optimisation of Matrix Alloy

The modulus data obtained for the Al-9Si-3Cu composites are close to the theoretical values predicted for a random planar array of fibres and indicate strong fibre-matrix bonding. Metallography on polished sections showed a uniform distribution of fibre in the matrix and the complete absence of porosity, demonstrating the effectiveness of a process involving fibre preforms and liquid metal infiltration. The micrograph in Figure 11 shows an interface between reinforced and unreinforced regions of a composite containing 24 v/o fibre. Generally, in Al-Si alloys there is a marked change in the matrix microstructure due to the presence of fibres involving a reduction in grain size, a coarsening of the eutectic structure and the preferential nucleation of silicon at fibre boundaries. The net effects of these changes have been shown to lead to an increase in inter-fibre matrix hardness and a decrease in overall ductility (9). These observations help to explain the low strain to failure values recorded and suggest that careful attention should be paid to matrix composition to avoid the embrittling effect of intermetallics and precipitates if the full room temperature strengthening potential is to be realised. Such considerations are of key importance in low temperature fatigue studies but are less critical at higher temperatures as the strength of the alloy falls off and the composite displays marginal plastic deformation.

Figure 11. Showing an unreinforced-reinforced interface in a squeeze cast Al-9Si-3Cu composite containing 24 v/o fibre

In order to understand better the effect of avoiding embrittling constituents, composites based on commercial purity aluminium (LMO), Al-2.5Mg and Al-10Mg (LM10) were prepared containing 20 v/o fibre. Easy wetting of the fibres is a particular feature of all the high pressure infiltration work carried out to-date, even with the LMO material. The presence of silica at the fibre surface may have an important effect in controlling interfacial behaviour, but despite intensive investigations (8, 9) no evidence of any significant reaction zone has been detected at the fibre-matrix interface.

Table III summarises the UTS and strain to failure data obtained at 25°C.

Table III. Effect of Increasing Alloy Magnesium Level

Matrix	UTS (MPa)	Strain to Failure (%)
Al	188	4.0
Al-2.5Mg	196	3.3
Al-10Mg	280	1.3

The results show that strain to failure values of the order of 3-4% may be achieved with highly ductile matrices but once second phases, such as Mg_2Al_3 or Mg_2Al_3 in the case of LM10, segregate at grain boundaries then ductility falls quite sharply. The role of fibres acting as nucleation sites during metal solidification is illustrated by the micrographs in Figures 12 and 13. Figure 12 shows an optical micrograph of a polished LM10 composite and Figure 13 a scanning electron micrograph of the same material after etching with Keller's reagent. It will be noted that the fibres are located mainly at grain boundaries and have effected a reduction in grain size.

Figure 12. Optical micrograph of LM10 composite showing fibres at grain boundaries

Figure 13. SEM showing LM10 composite after etching with Keller's reagent

Composites Produced by Powder Metallurgy

Three small composite billets were prepared by DWA Composite Specialties Inc from Al-6061 powder and milled alumina fibre. Metallographic examination of polished sections cut from the as-pressed billets indicated that they contained thin laminar regions void of fibre, separating other areas in which the fibre distribution was very good. The micrographs in Figures 14 and 15 illustrate this point. However, in view of the fact that this represents the first serious attempt to incorporate these fibres by the powder route the results are generally very encouraging.

The billets, reinforced with 29 v/o fibre, were given a solution treatment at 520°C for 1 hour followed by a cold water quench and a precipitation stage at 150°C for 24 hours. As a result of this treatment, the UTS values of the billets increased by 67-81% but the modulus values did not appear to change significantly. The heating also introduced much more scatter in the tensile data, probably reflecting the variable fibre distribution in the materials but this may also be indicative of non-optimum heat treatment conditions. The tensile data are summarised below in Table IV and the strength:density ratio of the three composites are compared with published data for the unreinforced alloy in Figure 16.

Figure 14. Al-6061 - 29 v/o fibre composite showing good fibre distribution

Figure 15. Showing thin laminar unreinforced region in an Al-6061-29 v/o fibre composite

Table IV. Summary of Tensile Data (25°C) on Powder-Based Composites

Billet	UTS (MPa)	Yield Strength (MPa)	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Strain to Failure (%)
I	317-378 (355)	210-263 (241)	71-108 (91)	1.3-1.7 (1.5)
II	377-383 (380)	224-293 (262)	91-103 (97)	1.5-1.6 (1.6)
III	409-451 (428)	332-355 (343)	94-98 (96)	1.1-1.3 (1.2)

Notes: (i) Average values are given in brackets
 (ii) Yield strength determined by 0.2% strain value

The results point to average UTS increases over the reinforced alloy of 13, 21 and 36% for billets I, II and III respectively, and average modulus increases of 28, 37 and 35%. The higher performance of billet III is very encouraging and warrants further examination. More generally, the effect of hot working the billets could usefully be investigated. Extrusion, for example, should introduce significant fibre alignment,

improve uniformity of the composites and can be expected to increase ductility. On the negative side, there may be an adverse effect on fibre length which could affect high temperature performance since the effective stress transfer length will increase with increasing temperature. In this current work fibres recovered from the as-pressed composites had lengths ranging from 30 microns up to over 200 microns, with an average value of around 90 microns.

Figure 16. Strength: density ratios of three Al-6061-29 v/o fibre composites

The tensile strengths of the composites have been measured up to 400°C and are plotted in Figure 17. The data points were derived from average values obtained at each temperature for the two billets (I and III) showing the highest and lowest strength at 25°C. The properties of a 20 v/o fibre composite produced by squeeze casting and given the same heat treatment are plotted on the same graph for comparison. Table V lists the tensile strength, modulus and strain to failure data recorded for the squeeze cast (SC) and powder-based (PM) material.

The results show that the differences in UTS values of the composites at 25°C are eroded with increasing temperature and become insignificant above 250-300°C. Comparing the results for the powder-based material with the squeeze cast composite, it seems that the higher fibre loading in the former compensates for a less uniform fibre distribution. Generally, in terms of strength, fibre reinforcement increases the working temperature of the alloy by 100-150°C.

Table V. Comparison of Tensile Data obtained on Squeeze Cast (SC) and Powder (PM) Composites

Temp (°C)	Vol Fraction Fibre/ Composite Type	Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Strain to Failure (%)
25	0.29/PM	355-428*	91-96*	1.5-1.2*
25	0.20/SC	362	92	1.1
200	0.29/PM	260-310	84-88	1.5-1.3
200	0.20/SC	270		
300	0.29/PM	165	76	1.9
300	0.20/SC	165	79	1.8
400	0.29/PM	70-80	66	2.5
400	0.20/SC	75	66	2.4

* Where there is a range of results quoted for the powder-based material this indicates a difference between billets I and II (ie the composites which showed the highest and lowest average strengths at 25°C)

Figure 17. The elevated temperature tensile strengths of Al-6061-based composites produced by powder metallurgy (29 v/o fibre) and squeeze casting (20 v/o fibre) compared with unreinforced alloy

Conclusions

1 The three most important properties conferred on aluminium alloys by short staple alumina fibre reinforcement are retention of strength at elevated temperatures, greatly enhanced modulus and controllable wear resistance. These properties have been exploited in the reinforcement of pistons for advanced diesel engines and further applications are anticipated in gudgeon pin bosses, connecting rods, cylinder liners, valve seats and turbo charger impellers.

2 If the initial promise of the powder metallurgical route to composites is fulfilled and consistent property data are achieved on scale-up, the relatively low price of the fibres at around \$30/kg and a density of 3.3 g/cm³ suggest potential for structural applications requiring strength and stiffness enhancement at temperatures below 200°C. The next phase of development work is to assess the secondary forming capability of the composites.

3 A particularly important target for future research is to increase composite ductility. In view of the significant effect of fibres on matrix microstructure, it would seem desirable to tailor alloy chemistry and heat treatment conditions to the fibre properties in order to achieve optimum composite performance.

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